

ASSESSMENT WITH CORRECTION OF LIPID PEROXIDATION SYNDROME AND LIVER FUNCTIONAL STATUS IN RHINOSINUSITIS WITH COMORBIDITY OF CHRONIC OBSTRUCTIVE PULMONARY DISEASE

Saliakhunova Kh.O. ¹

Shaikhova Kh.E. ²

Usmanova N.A. ¹

¹ Andijan State Medical Institute. Andijan, Uzbekistan.

² Tashkent Medical Academy, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

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Relevance. Analysis of modern literature data confirms the concept of interaction between ENT organs and lower respiratory tract. However, assessment and correction of endogenous intoxication syndrome, lipid peroxidation and functional status of the liver against the background of comorbidity of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) in rhinosinusitis remains insufficiently studied. Additional studies are needed to deeply understand the pathogenesis, the impact of comorbidity of the upper and lower respiratory tract on each other, as well as on the detoxification potential of the body to develop optimal interdisciplinary approaches to diagnosis and treatment.

Aim. Assessment and correction of lipid peroxidation levels and functional status of the liver in rhinosinusitis with comorbidity of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD).

Materials and methods of the study. The work was carried out according to the research plan of the Andijan State Medical Institute at the clinical base of the Otolaryngology Department for the period from 2020 to 2023. In accordance with the inclusion/exclusion criteria, at the first stage of the study of the incidence rate, COPD was detected in 64 (36%) patients out of 178 patients with rhinosinusitis. The incidence of COPD in patients with acute rhinosinusitis (ARS) was 13.5% - 24 patients, and in 40 patients with chronic rhinosinusitis (CRS) - 22.5%. For further study of lipid peroxidation in patients with rhinosinusitis, we identified 2 study groups and one group from the pulmonology department of the institute's clinic with isolated COPD for comparative analysis. Group 1: 24 (25.5%) patients with acute rhinosinusitis with COPD; Group 2: 40 (42.6%) patients with chronic rhinosinusitis and COPD; Group 3: 30 (31.9%) patients with COPD. Depending on the methods of treatment, the fight against lipid peroxidation syndrome, all study groups were divided into the following subgroups: Group 1 was divided into subgroups A and

B, 12 (12.76%) patients each, in which standard therapy was carried out in subgroup A, and in subgroup B, sorption-antioxidant therapy was included in the complex of standard treatment measures. Group 2 (patients with CRS and COPD) was also divided into subgroups A and B, 20 (21.28%) patients each, and in these subgroups, standard and sorption-antioxidant treatment were also carried out. The condition of patients, biochemical blood parameters, lipid peroxidation level, and results of dynamic treatment assessment were compared with the control group (3rd group, n=30) of patients with isolated COPD. In all three study groups, the main clinical, functional, instrumental, laboratory examinations and treatments were carried out according to the recommendations, GOLD 2020, EPOS 2020 and the approved protocol of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Results and discussion. Scientific interest in the process of lipid peroxidation has increased especially in connection with the clarification of their role in the pathogenesis of many diseases. Damage to biomembranes and associated functions of most integral and near-membrane proteins, including receptors, transport and structure-forming proteins, enzymes and enzyme systems of both the plasma membrane and membranes of various subcellular organelles, disrupt the course of many cellular processes and the functioning of the cell as a whole. The effectiveness of complex combined therapy using sorption-antioxidant therapy can also be traced by the dynamics of lipid peroxidation indices. Upon admission to hospital, in patients with ARS with COPD, the level of MDA in the blood plasma in the 1-B subgroup of patients exceeded normal values by 3.6 times. Under the influence of sorption-antioxidant therapy in the complex of standard treatment, the level of this indicator in this subgroup of patients on the 3rd day of the treatment period decreased by 45.2% and was significantly lower than the initial indicator ($p < 0.05$). A significant decrease in this indicator in patients with CRS with comorbid COPD was also noted on the 3rd day of treatment by 46.0%. In patients with ARS and CRS with COPD, as well as in patients with COPD without rhinosinusitis, a significant decrease in the MDA concentration was noted on the 7th day of the treatment period by 49%, 47.2% and 46.3%, respectively. By this time, in patients with ARS and CRS with COPD, who underwent sorption-antioxidant therapy, it was 1.6 and 1.9 times lower than in subgroups 1-A and 1-B, and 1.6 and 1.8 times lower in group 3, respectively. This once again confirms the advantage of sorption-antioxidant therapy in comparison with standard treatment methods.

The level of concentration of DK in the blood of patients with ARS with COPD (1-A and 1-B subgroups) upon admission to the hospital exceeded the normal values by an average of 1.9 and 2 times, respectively. Under the influence of complex treatment with the use of sorption-antioxidant therapy, the level of concentration of DK in the 1-B subgroup of patients already on the 3rd day of the treatment period decreased to $3.53 \pm 0.12 \mu\text{mol} / \text{l}$ (by 29.1%) and significantly differed from the initial data. As a result of the complex treatment using sorption-antioxidant therapy in patients with CRS with COPD, on the 3rd day of treatment, the level of DK in the blood plasma decreased by 43.8% (1.6 times lower than in the 2-A subgroup of patients by this time) and reached normal values - $2.68 \pm 0.09 \mu\text{mol} / \text{l}$, whereas in the 3rd group of patients the level of this indicator still remained high. The effectiveness of the use of sorption-antioxidant therapy against the background of standard treatment can be traced by the dynamics of a number of indicators of the functional state of the liver.

In patients with ARS with comorbid COPD (subgroup 1-B), the total bilirubin content in the blood upon admission reached $53.4 \pm 2.3 \mu\text{mol}/\text{l}$, and in patients with CRS with comorbid COPD (subgroup 2-B), this indicator increased to $51.5 \pm 2.1 \mu\text{mol}/\text{l}$. Against the background of complex combination therapy, the level of total bilirubin in both subgroups significantly decreased on the 3rd day ($27.5 \pm 1.3 \mu\text{mol}/\text{l}$, $24.4 \pm 1.3 \mu\text{mol}/\text{l}$), which is 48.5% and 52.6% ($p < 0.05$) relative to the baseline data, respectively. In subgroups 1-B and 2-B of patients, the level of total bilirubin normalized on the 7th day. By this time, the level of this indicator in COPD patients decreased by 48.4%, and in subgroup 1-A by 43.5% relative to the initial data, but had not yet reached normal values. The level of alkaline phosphatase in patients of subgroup 1-B on day 3 decreased by 18.8%, and in patients of subgroup 2-B it decreased by 21.8% and was significantly lower than the initial level ($p < 0.05$). In the following days, the level of this indicator continued to decrease and on the 7th day of complex treatment it reached normal values (in subgroup 1-B - $89.6 \pm 1.2 \text{ U/L}$; in subgroup 2-B - $87.2 \pm 1.1 \text{ U/L}$). This is 1.7 and 1.8 times less than on admission ($p < 0.05$). In the 3rd group of patients with isolated COPD, the alkaline phosphatase level was normalized on the 7th day, but still remained at the upper limits of the normal value. A significant decrease in the activity of liver enzymes (AST/ALT) was also noted on the 3rd day (by 63.5% and 60.7%, respectively) against the background of sorption-antioxidant therapy in patients with ARS with COPD, and in patients with CRS with comorbidity of COPD, the level of liver enzymes by

this time significantly decreased by 56.8% and 57.8%, respectively ($p > 0.05$). In patients with COPD (group 3), a significant decrease in the AST/ALT level (by 40.3% and 32.6%) was noted only on the 7th day of treatment. The creatinine level in patients with ARS with COPD significantly decreased on the 3rd day of treatment (by 45.6%), and in patients with CRS with COPD by 47.4% and almost reached normal values. In group 3, a significant decrease in this indicator was noted on the 7th day of the treatment process by 8.5% ($114.7 \pm 3.5 \mu\text{mol/l}$) relative to the initial data. The urea level against the background of complex therapy with sorption-antioxidant therapy in patients with acute and chronic rhinosinusitis with comorbidity of COPD on the 3rd day decreased by 34.8% and 36.8%, respectively, relative to the initial data ($p < 0.05$).

Prothrombin (INR) is one of the criteria for assessing the functional state of the liver. In patients with ARS with comorbid COPD against the background of standard therapy, the level of this indicator was reduced compared to the initial data on the 3rd day of the treatment period by 6.25%, and in patients with CRS with COPD by 6.7%. Against the background of complex treatment with sorption-antioxidant therapy, the INR level by this time in patients 1-B and 2-B significantly decreased by 11.8% and 16.7% ($p < 0.05$), respectively. On the 7th day of treatment, the difference in the decrease in the INR level between subgroups A and B was reliable by 23.1% and 30.8%, and with group 3 of patients with COPD - by 16.7% and 25%, respectively.

Conclusions. Lipid peroxidation in rhinosinusitis with comorbid COPD is caused by the development of systemic inflammation with an increase in the level of endogenous intoxication markers and excessive accumulation of lipid peroxidation products (MDA - increased by 3.6 times; DK - increased by 2.0 times). Liver damage occurs, as evidenced by significant changes in the studied indicators of its functional status upon admission of patients to the hospital. At the same time, it is noteworthy that the restoration of the functional status of the liver in the chronic form of rhinosinusitis against the background of complex therapy occurs comparatively faster than in the acute form of this disease with COPD. The obtained data indicate that the use of the method of sorption-antioxidant therapy in the complex of standard treatment is rational and, mutually complementing each other, has a pronounced hepatoprotective and antihypoxic effect, significantly reduces the intensification of endogenous intoxication and lipid peroxidation processes in the body, the functional load on the liver and kidneys, and allows for a more complete use of their detoxification potential.

